

EMPLOYEE JOB SATISFACTION MODEL BASED ON CAREER DEVELOPMENT

BUDI KRISNA LELMALAYA^{1*}, ANOESYIRWAN MOEINS² and MARHALINDA³

^{1,2,3}Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Persada Indonesia Y.A.I, Jakarta.

Email: ¹budikrisnal.2166390035@upi-yai.ac.id (*Corresponding Author), ²anoesyirwan.moein@upi-yai.ac.id,

³marhalinda@upi-yai.ac.id

Abstract

This study aims to analyze and answer the research gap in various research results and phenomena that occur where career development in this study functions as an intervening variable and is inconsistently considered by employees to produce good work performance. This type of research is quantitative descriptive with the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis method on the LISREL application. The research objects used in this study were employees at PT GMF AeroAsia Tbk at various airports in Indonesia with a population of 1,548 employees and a total of 318 employees were obtained. The results of this study can be explained that all exogenous variables in this study can explain their influence significantly on endogenous variables, except for hypothesis-2, organizational justice cannot explain the career development of employees of PT. GMF Aero Asia Tbk. These results are expected to help practitioners in organizing and maximizing human resources owned by any company.

Keywords: Transformation Leadership, Organizational Justice, Competence, Career Development, Job Satisfaction.

1. INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

In the relevant previous research results, according to Miston Mapuranga et al., (2021) who suggested that to strengthen and enrich the results of their research related to employee job satisfaction influenced by procedural justice; workplace spirituality; and work locus of control, then in future research, relevant variables can be studied which also have implications for overall job satisfaction. Meanwhile, according to Nenin Kartika Sari (2019), for further research, it can review more similar journals that are relevant to other variables that influence job satisfaction and organizational justice. Thus, it can establish better conceptual and operational constructions.

Other research results in Ariska Adittyia, et al. (2021) stated that the results of their research could be an alternative solution and important consideration in the reference source process for further research on competence, motivation, career development, and performance. Then you can consider additional variables studied, such as organizational justice and transformational leadership.

The role of leadership is vital in the career advancement of an employee. Previous research related to these two variables is research by Warit Wipulanusat, et. Al, (2018), the results explain that innovation leadership has an influence on the career development of engineering professionals at the Australian Public Services. I Komang Triyana Dharma et al. (2021) in their research wanted to find out the influence of transformational leadership on career development, it was found that transformational leadership style has a positive and significant influence on

employee career development at PT. Gapura Angkasa - Denpasar. In line with the research results of Minseo Kim and Terry A. Beehr (2017) which stated that empowering leadership has an effect on the career development of full-time employees working in the United States.

According to Gibson, et al. (2012:356) transformational leadership should be able to encourage motivation and influence for employees to achieve greater work performance than planned. Meanwhile, according to Priatna and Limakrisna (2021:57), career development is a form of unity of every element of an employee's activities in their work life in improving and developing themselves, where these activities are carried out officially by a company based on the intention to obtain a balance between individual positions and positions determined by the company. A good leader will of course always pay attention to the development of the competence and careers of its members in a better direction.

Career ladder is an individual's work history or a series of positions held during their working life. During an employee's career journey, it is also determined by fair management decisions. Previous research related to this variable is research from Nadeem-Uz-Zaman, et al. (2022), the results show that there is an influence of organizational justice on employee career development. In Khan, Junaid Athar, et al. (2017) in their research wanted to find out the influence of organizational justice on career development, the results showed that distributive and interactional justice had a significant effect while procedural justice had no impact on employee career satisfaction in the public sector in Pakistan. In line with the results of research from Saraih U. N. et, al. (2019) who argued that there is a significant and positive influence of organizational justice on employee careers. According to Busro (2018) from the perspective of HR management, organizational justice is the rights received by employees based on their level of education, job position, structure, duties and functions, contributions to the organization and work experience, as well as opportunities for improving abilities and competencies that are received fairly which are useful in developing employee careers based on the rules in a company.

Among the determinants of career development, one of them is determined by the employee's competency required by the company. Previous research related to these two variables is research by Ariska Adittyia, et al. (2021), the results of the study showed that competence has a significant influence on career development. Nurul Aini et.al. (2020) in their research wanted to find out the effect of competence on career development, the results showed that employee competence has a significant influence on the stage of career development and employee performance. This is in line with the results of research by Ahmad Faisol, et al. (2022) by stating that competence has a significant influence on career development and employee performance.

The results in Colquitt, LePine and Wesson (2015:199) competence is an employee's belief in their ability to succeed in work. Competence is identical to the concept of self-efficacy, namely a belief that employees can carry out certain behaviors needed to complete work effectively and efficiently. Competence is the ability of an employee to understand the purpose of his work by having a good attitude, knowledge, skills and actions when doing work, and understand the

importance of discipline in the company so that all rules can be obeyed so that in the end it can provide success in work performance, job satisfaction and a good career path.

When employee career development is hampered, it will have an impact on the operational side of the company. Employees will think that there is no benefit to being loyal to work for a long time if there is no career advancement. For millennial employees who have good competence, leaving the company is an easy matter, this will certainly be detrimental to the company because it will lose employees who have good competence and qualifications and have been fostered for a certain time. For this reason, important steps are needed by the company in developing employee careers such as paying attention to leadership styles that are in accordance with organizational changes and developing employee abilities and competencies fairly so that employee career paths can be planned properly in accordance with company regulations.

Previous studies related to these four variables are studies conducted by Angga Karta Puspito, et.al. (2020), Sobia Shabeer, et al. (2020), Siti Mujanah (2020), the results show that there is an influence of transformational leadership, organizational justice, and competence on employee career development. According to Veithzal Rivai (2017:21) career development is an increase in an individual's work ability in terms of achievement with the aim of achieving the desired job and career. Of course, this career development is carried out by direct superiors and determined by the management of a company.

Transformational leadership will motivate employees to carry out more challenging things than usual and also achieve these challenges in accordance with the company's vision and mission. Transformational leaders tend to have a commitment to making their team members more satisfied at work. Transformational leaders empower and pay attention to employee needs and also develop the abilities of employees who have the potential to lead in the future. Previous research relevant to the two variables is from Rawan Alafeshat and Cem Tanova (2019), the results show that servant leadership has a positive and significant influence on the level of job satisfaction of Jordanian airline employees. Simanungkalit, et.al. (2019) in his research wanted to find out the influence of leadership models on the level of job satisfaction, the results showed that the most dominant leadership influencing the level of job satisfaction of PT Lion Mentari Airlines employees was an authoritarian leader with a coefficient of 0.181, a partisan leader coefficient value of 0.161, and a paternalistic leader with a coefficient of -0.191. While the results of the study by Cecep Pahrudin, et al. (2018) stated that ethical leadership and aspects of work with character have a positive impact on employee job satisfaction at Indonesian airlines.

In Rothwell, et al. (2016) transformational leadership style is a leadership that can change its employees to develop better than their personal interests and challenge or stimulate employees in pursuing a goal of the company. Transformational leadership must be able to provide job satisfaction and change employee thinking from just working to fulfill their individual needs, but also participating in fighting to achieve the company's goals together. In a company, the role of justice towards employees is quite important in maintaining the level of job satisfaction. Previous research related to these two variables is a study produced by Okan & Bayraktar

(2021), the results show that there is a good relationship between organizational justice and the level of employee job satisfaction. The highest level of relationship was found between procedural justice and employee job satisfaction of airlines in Turkey. Miston Mapuranga, et al. (2021) in their research wanted to find out the influence of organizational justice on the level of job satisfaction, the results showed that procedural justice has a positive influence and plays a role in increasing job satisfaction. In line with the results of the study by Nenin Kartika Sari (2019) which stated that there was an influence of organizational justice on the level of employee job satisfaction.

In the research results of Agustina Titien et al. (2022) organizational justice explains how much employees view them as being treated well and fairly according to normal, reasonable, fair and equal standards for each other based on the level of moral and ethical standardization that applies to the company where they work and also how this perception will affect employee commitment and job satisfaction. According to Widyatmojo, et.al. (2021) to assess the ethics of a company, it can be seen from how fairly the company treats employees. Unfair actions can damage morale, increase stress levels, and have a negative impact on the work environment. Injustice within an organization can result in decreased employee satisfaction and commitment to the company. Competence is the ability of an employee to understand the purpose of his work by having a good attitude, knowledge, skills, and actions when carrying out tasks and understanding how important a disciplined attitude is in the company by obeying the rules so that in the end it can provide success in work performance, job satisfaction and a good career path. Previous research related to these two variables is research from Lira Agusinta, et al. (2021), the results of the study are that the level of employee competence contributes to the job satisfaction of employees of PT. Jasa Angkasa Semesta Jakarta.

Bülent Ulutürk and Recep Tayfun (2019) in their research wanted to find out the effect of competency variables on job satisfaction, the results showed that competence had a significant effect on the level of job satisfaction of employees working at Turkish Airports. In line with the research of Cindy Christine Miranda, et al. (2020) by stating that there is a positive and significant influence of competence on the level of job satisfaction of employees in the Power Generation Industry in Indonesia. According to Priatna and Limakrisna (2021:101) competence can be interpreted as a number of attitudes and behaviors of knowledge, abilities, possessed by an employee to complete a job which can ultimately provide success in work performance, job satisfaction and a good career. Several things that have an influence on competence come from internal & external which can be controlled by an employee, meaning that it can be developed to an optimal stage through education, training, facilities and infrastructure, and even support from leaders.

Career development is an ongoing process for an employee, involving a series of formal levels designed by the company's management. This process aims to develop human resources to meet the needs of the company. Employee job satisfaction can be obtained through an effective career development program, which is implemented by direct superiors and management. In Nita Tri Febrianti, et.al. (2020), the results of her study showed that career development has a positive impact on job satisfaction. In line with the results of a study conducted by Aulia

Rahman et.al. (2021) which also confirmed that there is a correlation between career development and employee job satisfaction. According to Mathis and Jackson (2018) career development is a series of positions and positions related to the work carried out by an employee in his work life, and each employee will tend to pursue his career until his individual needs are satisfied. The results in Sitinjak, et. al. (2021) career development is a form of approach or activity that is formally arranged by the company which is useful for increasing job satisfaction, growth, knowledge and abilities of an employee so that they can work with competencies and experience that are in accordance with the requirements of a company.

In the world of work, especially in the aircraft maintenance industry, high employee satisfaction factors are something that management needs to pay attention to in maintaining employee existence to support the achievement of the organization's vision and mission. Companies need to pay attention to, strengthen and improve job satisfaction. The success of a company depends on various aspects, including human resources which are a key factor. Therefore, in order for employees to have high job satisfaction, management must pay fair attention to employee career development and also improve competency so that work capabilities can continue to be improved. If performance is less than optimal, there is a risk that the company's targets cannot be achieved appropriately. Previous research related to these five variables is a study by Sherwin Ian D., et al., (2021), Alvianto Nuryadi (2020), Haryadi and Nunung Nurhasanah (2021), Yusuf Ronny Edward and Lila Maria Kaban (2020), Hassan Barau Singhry (2018) the results show that there is an influence of transformational leadership, organizational justice, competence and career development on job satisfaction.

According to Robbins and Judge (2019:46) the form of job satisfaction is a good attitude in working based on an evaluation of the characteristics of the job in general. Employees in working need; interaction with superiors and coworkers, have competencies according to requirements, comply with all company procedures and policies, according to standards and performance. Therefore, leaders should pay more attention to employee satisfaction in working, because it will have a positive effect on the effectiveness of the company so that later customers will be satisfied and the company's profits will increase.

2. HYPOTHESIS

H₁: There is an influence of Transformational Leadership on Employee Career Development.

H₂: There is an influence of Organizational Justice on Employee Career Development.

H₃: There is an influence of Competence on Employee Career Development.

H₄: There is an influence of Transformational Leadership on Employee Job Satisfaction.

H₅: There is an influence of Organizational Justice on Employee Job Satisfaction.

H₆: There is an influence of Competence on Employee Job Satisfaction.

H₇: There is an influence of Employee Career Development on Employee Job Satisfaction

Figure 1: Research Framework Model

3. RESEARCH METHODS

This research is a descriptive study using a quantitative approach with hypothesis testing with the object of this research being employees of PT GMF AeroAsia Tbk located at Soekarno-Hatta International Airport Jakarta, and branch offices in Indonesia, namely, Kualanamu International Airport Medan, Juanda International Airport Surabaya, I Gusti Ngurah Rai International Airport Bali, and Sultan Hasanuddin International Airport Makassar with a time span from August 2022 to November 2023.

The target population is 4,890 direct and indirect non-structural employees, while the target population in this study is 1,548 indirect employees (non-aircraft technicians) with the staff position category (engineering, planner, purchaser, analyst, business support) who work at Base Maintenance and Line Maintenance PT GMF AeroAsia Tbk Soekarno-Hatta International Airport Jakarta (1437 employees), Medan branch office (17 employees), Surabaya (28 employees), and Denpasar (41 employees) and Makassar (25 employees).

The sampling technique uses the probability sampling method, simple random sampling, which means taking a sample member from the population randomly without considering the population strata. The technique for determining the number of samples taken is to use the Slovin/Yamane formula because it considers time and cost limitations.

According to Sugiyono (2017) if the population size is known, then the calculation can use the Slovin/Yamane formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n = sample size

N = population size of 1548

e = sampling error rate, which is 5%.

The results of the sample size calculation are as follows:

$$n = \frac{1.548}{1 + 1.548 (0,05)^2}$$

$$n = 318$$

The number of samples obtained was 317.86 which was rounded up to 318 samples. Meanwhile, to focus on the population area to be more efficient, Sampling Fraction Cluster was used, namely:

$$S = \frac{\text{Permanent Employee Population Per Service}}{N} \times n$$

Where:

S = Sample size in proportion

n = Number of Samples

N = Population size of 1,548

Operational Variables:

Table 1: Operational Career Development Variables

Variables	Concept	Dimensions	Indicators	Questionnaire Code	Scale
Career Development (Y1)	Career development is a career system that is planned and implemented in a structured and sustainable manner by management, the aim of which is to provide career clarity for employees and	Fair Treatment	Fair career development opportunities.	PK1	Likert
			Promotions are made with objective considerations and are widely known by employees.	PK2	
		Concern from Direct Superior	The direct superior guides employees in their careers.	PK3	
			The direct superior creates employee career development programs.	PK4	

Variables	Concept	Dimensions	Indicators	Questionnaire Code	Scale
	certainty of job fulfillment in a company.	Promotion Opportunity Information	Access open information about job promotion opportunities.	PK5	Likert
			Direct superiors provide information on promotional opportunities.	PK6	
		Individual Ability	Have the ability to be promoted to a higher level.	PK7	Likert
			Have good abilities, skills and attitudes to support career development.	PK8	
		Opportunities to Grow	Get the opportunity to improve their abilities and competencies.	PK9	Likert
			Opportunity to get training and certification.	PK10	
		Mentors and Sponsors	Mentors and sponsors are available for career development.	PK11	Likert
			Mentors and sponsors are needed in the employee career development process.	PK12	

Table 2: Operational Variables of Job Satisfaction

Variables	Concept	Dimensions	Indicators	Questionnaire Code	Scale
Job Satisfaction (Y2)	Employee job satisfaction is an evaluation that describes an individual employee's attitude of satisfaction or dissatisfaction with the differences that arise between what is desired and what is actually received while working at a company.	Salary and Benefits	Fair salary and allowances.	KK1	Likert
			Salary and allowances received are sufficient to meet needs	KK2	
		Trust in Leaders	A sense of trust in direct superiors and company leaders.	KK3	Likert
			Flow of employee career development information.	KK4	
		Intrinsic Job Factors	Work done according to ability.	KK5	Likert
			Work done with pleasure.	KK6	
		Working Conditions	Facilities and infrastructure are adequate to support work.	KK7	Likert
			Conducive working conditions and situations.	KK8	

Variables	Concept	Dimensions	Indicators	Questionnaire Code	Scale
		Fairness	Fair treatment of employees	KK9	Likert
			Rules implemented by management to influence employee work behavior.	KK10	
		Opportunity To Advance	Open opportunities for improving work skills.	KK11	Likert
			Company management's attention to employee development.	KK12	

Table 3: Operational Variables of Transformational Leadership

Variables	Concept	Dimensions	Indicators	Questionnaire Code	Scale
Transformational Leadership (X ₁)	Transformational leadership is a leadership that is oriented towards change that focuses on the process and products produced, always providing motivation and positive energy to employees to make extra efforts in working and accepting tasks given without burden, and happily doing every job in line with changes in the organization's vision..	Organizational Awareness	Understand the scope, function, role, and responsibility towards employees.	KT1	Likert
			Able to make and oversee changes in accordance with the company's vision and mission.	KT2	
		Leadership	Employees are motivated and directed to make changes in achieving targets effectively and efficiently.	KT3	Likert
			Have empathy and interpersonal skills towards employees.	KT4	
		Developing Others	Have a structured employee development program.	KT5	Likert
			Employee coaching and development programs are explained directly to employees.	KT6	
		Change Leadership	Adjusting work processes using new, more effective and efficient methods and methods.	KT7	Likert
			Actively encouraging themselves and employees to come up with new and innovative ideas that have a positive impact on achieving company goals.	KT8	
		Interpersonal Communication	Communicate employee development programs openly to employees.	KT9	Likert
			Provide feedback on the work employees do.	KT10	

Table 4: Operational Variables of Organizational Justice

Variables	Concept	Dimensions	Indicators	Questionnaire Code	Scale
Organizational Justice (X ₂)	Organizational justice is the employee's perception of the extent to which they are treated fairly, justly and equally by their leaders or management, in accordance with the regulations and values that apply in the company where they work, where this perception can influence employee commitment, job satisfaction and performance.	Distributive Justice	Fairness of perceived work results.	KO1	Likert
			All employees have the same rights in getting results or decisions.	KO2	
			The awards received by employees are balanced with the hard work given to the company.	KO3	
		Procedural Justice	Decisions are taken based on accurate and complete work results.	KO4	Likert
			Employee perception of decisions for development and career.	KO5	
			Reward and punishment policies are implemented firmly.	KO6	
		Informational Justice	Employees are given honest and open explanations about development and career opportunities.	KO7	Likert
			Transparency and access to information about work obtained from direct superiors.	KO8	
			The company provides access to employees to obtain information.	KO9	
		Interpersonal Justice	Employees are treated with respect, attention and dignity.	KO10	Likert
			Continuous socialization from direct superiors.	KO11	
			The direct superior has empathy towards employees regarding working conditions..	KO12	

Table 5: Operational Competency Variables

Variables	Concept	Dimensions	Indicators	Questionnaire Code	Scale
Competence (X ₃)	Competence is the ability of an employee to have good knowledge, skills, attitudes and behavior as well as understand and comply with all the rules in completing a job and the results are in accordance with applicable targets and standards, so that in the end it can provide success in work performance, job satisfaction and a good career ladder.	Quality of Work	Quality of work according to standards.	KM1	Likert
			Careful in carrying out work.	KM2	
		Speed of Work	Have a fast work rhythm.	KM3	Likert
			Work results without errors.	KM4	
		Achievement Orientation	Work well and exceed established performance standards.	KM5	Likert
			Achieve high quality targets so that work performance is optimal.	KM6	
		Self Confidence	Appear confident in carrying out work.	KM7	Likert
			Have good thinking skills to always learn and develop themselves.	KM8	
		Teamwork and Collaboration	Able to work cooperatively with others.	KM9	Likert
			Demonstrate activeness by providing ideas when with a team.	KM10	
		Communication Skill	Able to communicate ideas and views using language that is easy to understand.	KM11	Likert
			Able to communicate well with team or other people.	KM12	

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

Analysis of Research Variable Description

Table 6: Score Range and Categories

Score	Interval Score	Answer	Category
1	1,00 - 1,79	Strongly disagree	Below average/Needs improvement
2	1,80 - 2,59	Disagree	Below average/Needs improvement
3	2,60 - 3,39	Somewhat disagree	Equal to average/Needs improvement
4	3,40 - 4,19	Agree	Above average/Maintained
5	4,20 - 5,00	Strongly agree	Above average/Maintained

Source: Sekaran and Bougie

Table 7: Hybrid Model Measurement Model Suitability - SEM

Goodness of Fit Indicator	Standard Value	Calculation Result	Conclusion
Absolute Fit Size			
<i>Goodness of Fit Index</i>	GF1 > 0,90	0.88	<i>Marginal Fit</i>
<i>Root Mean Square Error of Approximation</i>	RMSEA < 0,08	0.020	<i>Good Fit</i>
Incremental Fit Size			
<i>Normed Fit Index</i>	NFI > 0,90	0.99	<i>Good Fit</i>
<i>Non-Normed Fit Index</i>	NNFI > 0,90	1.00	<i>Good Fit</i>
<i>Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index</i>	AGFI > 0,90	0.85	<i>Marginal Fit</i>
<i>Relative Fit Index</i>	RFI > 0,90	0.99	<i>Good Fit</i>
<i>Incremental Fit Index</i>	IFI > 0,90	1.00	<i>Good Fit</i>
<i>Comparative Fit Index</i>	CFI > 0,90	1.00	<i>Good Fit</i>

Source: Processed data

Table 8: Hybrid Model Measurement Analysis - SEM

Construct	Dimension	SLF	Error	t-Value	Construct Reliability ($\geq 0,7$)	Variance Extract ($\geq 0,5$)	Test Results
Transformational Leadership (KT)	<i>Organizational Awareness (X1.1)</i>	0,71	0,5	14,51	0,70	0,556	Valid and Reliable
	<i>Leadership (X1.2)</i>	0,71	0,49	14,81			
	<i>Developing Others (X1.3)</i>	0,65	0,58	12,85			
	<i>Change Leadership (X1.4)</i>	0,89	0,21	33,67			
	<i>Interpersonal Communication (X1.5)</i>	0,75	0,44	18,07			
Organizational Justice (KO)	<i>Distributive Justice (X2.1)</i>	0,84	0,29	35,98	0,916	0,740	Valid and Reliable
	<i>Procedural Justice (X2.2)</i>	0,86	0,25	50,90			
	<i>Informational Justice (X2.3)</i>	0,94	0,11	80,35			

Construct	Dimension	SLF	Error	t-Value	Construct Reliability ($\geq 0,7$)	Variance Extract ($\geq 0,5$)	Test Results
	<i>Interpersonal Justice (X2.4)</i>	0,86	0,26	45,84			
Competence (KM)	<i>Quality of Work (X3.1)</i>	0,86	0,26	31,22	0,832	0,666	Valid and Reliable
	<i>Speed of Work (X3.2)</i>	0,73	0,47	16,23			
	<i>Achievement Orientation (X3.3)</i>	0,81	0,35	33,57			
	<i>Self Confidence (X3.4)</i>	0,69	0,53	18,14			
	<i>Teamwork and Collaboration(X3.5)</i>	0,86	0,25	39,71			
	<i>Communication Skill (X3.6)</i>	0,92	0,15	45,83			
Career Development (PK)	Fair Treatment (Y1.1)	0,85	0,27	-	0,896	0,715	Valid and Reliable
	Concern From Direct Superiors (Y1.2)	0,81	0,34	21,34			
	Promotion Opportunity Information (Y1.3)	0,86	0,26	25,01			
	Individual Ability (Y1.4)	0,83	0,31	23,72			
	Opportunity To Grow (Y1.5)	0,87	0,25	25,39			
	Mentors and Sponsors (Y1.6)	0,85	0,28	24,58			
Job satisfaction (KK)	Salary and Benefits (Y2.1)	0,82	0,32	-	0,812	0,627	Valid and Reliable
	Trust in Leaders (Y2.2)	0,72	0,48	18,20			
	Intrinsic Job Factors (Y2.3)	0,73	0,46	17,19			
	Working Conditions (Y2.4)	0,82	0,33	22,95			
	Justice (Y2.5)	0,82	0,32	20,9			
	Opportunity To Advance (Y2.6)	0,83	0,32	22,36			

Source: Processed data

Table 9: Summary of Latent Variable Inter-Test Results

No.	Path	Path Coefficient	t-Value >1,96	Test Results
1.	KT → PK	0,27	2,89	Significant
2.	KO → PK	0,09	1,16	Not Significant
3.	KM → PK	0,51	2,96	Significant
4.	KT → KK	0,20	2,51	Significant
5.	KO → KK	0,33	3,54	Significant
6.	KM → KK	0,28	2,96	Significant
7.	PK → KK	0,20	2,52	Significant

Source: Processed data

Persamaan Sub Struktural 1

$$PK = 0.27*KT + 0.092*KO + 0.51*KM, \text{ Errorvar.} = 0.34, R^2 = 0.66$$

(0.093) (0.079) (0.098) (0.048)
2.89 1.16 5.23 7.02

Model Sub Struktural 2 (t-Value)

$$KK = 0.20*PK + 0.20*KT + 0.33*KO + 0.28*KM, \text{ Errorvar.} = 0.19, R^2 = 0.81$$

(0.079) (0.078) (0.094) (0.096) (0.039)
2.52 2.51 3.54 2.96 4.86

Figure 2: Hybrid Model (Full SEM) Standardized

Figure 3: Hybrid Model (Full SEM) t-Value

Figure 4: Results of Calculation Analysis and Discussion

Table 10: Hypothesis Test Results

Hypothesis Statement		Koefisien Jalur	<i>t-count</i>	Critical Value	Test Result
H1	Transformational leadership influences the career development of PT. GMF Aero Asia Tbk employees	0,27	2,89	1,96	Ha Accepted Transformational Leadership has an influence on the career development of PT. GMF Aero Asia Tbk employees.
H2	Organizational justice influences career development of PT. GMF Aero Asia Tbk employees	0,092	1,16	1,96	H₀ Accepted Organizational Justice has no significant influence on the Career Development of PT. GMF Aero Asia Tbk employees.
H3	Competence influences the career development of PT. GMF Aero Asia Tbk employees	0,51	5,23	1,96	Ha Accepted Competence has an influence on the career development of PT. GMF Aero Asia Tbk employees.
H4	Transformational leadership influences employee job satisfaction at PT. GMF Aero Asia Tbk	0,2	2,51	1,96	Ha Accepted Transformational leadership influences employee job satisfaction at PT. GMF Aero Asia Tbk
H5	Organizational justice influences employee job satisfaction at PT. GMF Aero Asia Tbk	0,33	3,54	1,96	Ha Accepted Organizational justice influences employee job satisfaction at PT. GMF Aero Asia Tbk
H6	Competence influences employee job satisfaction at PT. GMF Aero Asia Tbk	0,28	2,96	1,96	Ha Accepted Competence influences employee job satisfaction at PT. GMF Aero Asia Tbk
H7	Career development affects employee job satisfaction at PT. GMF Aero Asia Tbk	0,2	2,52	1,96	Ha Accepted Career development affects employee job satisfaction at PT. GMF Aero Asia Tbk

Source: Processed data

5. DISCUSSION

The results of this study are in line with Warit Wipulanusat, et. Al, (2018), with the explanation of the results being that innovation leadership has an influence on career development, also in I Komang Triyana Dharma et.al. (2021) which resulted in transformational leadership style having a positive and significant influence on employee career development. Transformational leadership should be able to encourage motivation and influence for employees to achieve greater work performance than planned, Gibson, et al. (2012).

The results in Priatna and Limakrisna (2021) career development is a form of unity of every element of an employee's activities in their work life in improving and developing themselves,

where these activities are carried out officially by a company based on the intention to obtain a balance between individual positions and positions determined by the company. A good leader will of course always pay attention to the development of the competencies and careers of his members towards a better direction.

The results of this study contradict the results in Nadeem-Uz-Zaman, et al. (2022), showing that the results show the influence of organizational justice on employee career development. Different results are also shown in Khan, Junaid Athar, et al. (2017) found that distributive and interactional justice have a significant effect while procedural justice has no impact on employee career satisfaction in the public sector. In line with the results of research from Saraih U. N. et, al. (2019) which argues that there is a significant and positive influence of organizational justice on employee careers.

One of the factors that determines career development is employee competency required by the company. This study supports the results of Ariska Adittyia, et.al. (2021), Nurul Aini, et.al. (2020), Ahmad Faisol, et al. (2022), their research results show that competence has a significant influence on career development.

In Rawan Alafeshat and Cem Tanova (2019), Simanungkalit, et.al. (2019), Rothwell, et al. (2016), the results show that servant leadership has a positive and significant influence on employee job satisfaction levels. Another thing is that transformational leadership style is a leadership that can change its employees to develop better from their personal interests and challenge or stimulate employees in pursuing a company goal. Transformational leadership must be able to provide job satisfaction and change employees' thinking from just working to fulfill their individual needs, but also participating in fighting to achieve the company's goals together.

This study is also in line with the results in Miston Mapuranga, et al. (2021), Okan & Bayraktar (2021), Nenin Kartika Sari (2019), Agustina Titien et al. (2022), Widyatmojo, et.al. (2021), it was found that procedural justice has a positive influence and plays a role in increasing job satisfaction. Another thing to assess the ethics of a company can be seen from how fairly the company treats employees. Unfair actions can damage morale, increase stress levels, and have a negative impact on the work environment. Injustice in the organization can result in decreased employee satisfaction and commitment to the company.

Competence is the ability of an employee to understand the purpose of his work by having a good attitude, knowledge, skills, and actions when carrying out tasks and understanding how important a disciplined attitude is in the company by complying with the rules so that in the end it can provide success in work performance, job satisfaction and a good career path. The results of other studies that are in line with the results of this study are in the results of Lira Agusinta, et.al. (2021), Bülent Ulutürk and Recep Tayfun (2019), Cindy Christine Miranda, et al. (2020), Priatna and Limakrisna (2021), with the results that the level of employee competence contributes to employee job satisfaction. Career development is an ongoing process for an employee, involving a series of formal levels designed by company management. This process aims to develop human resources to meet the needs of the company.

Employee job satisfaction can be obtained through an effective career development program, which is implemented by direct superiors and management. The results of the study strengthen the results in Wahid Sumarjo (2022), Nita Tri Febrianti, et.al. (2020) showed that career development has a significant influence on job satisfaction levels.

6. CONCLUSION

Competence is a dominant variable in the development of employee careers at PT. GMF Aero Asia Tbk, where the career development variable successfully mediates and can explain its influence on the research problem, namely job satisfaction.

Bibliography

- 1) Abdillah, Willy dkk. (2020), Concept and Application of Variant-Based Structural Equation Modeling in Business Research. Second Edition First Printing. Yogyakarta: UPP STIM YKPN.
- 2) Ahmad Faisol, Chamariyah, dan Subijanto. (2022). The Influence of HR Competence and Professionalism on Employee Performance Mediated by Career Development (Study on Employees of PT. Garam (Persero) in the Sampang Salt Field Area). Journal of Management Science and E-Commerce Publication. Vol.1.No.3.September2022.DOI:<https://doi.org/10.30640/digital.v1i3.539>.
- 3) Alvianto Nuryadi, E. Didik Subiyanto, Ignatius Soni Kurniawan. (2020). The Influence of Organizational Justice and Career Development on Job Satisfaction: With Organizational Commitment as Outcome Indonesian Journal of Management and Business. Vol 6, No 1, 2020. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.32528/jmbi.v6i1.3535>.
- 4) Angga Karta Puspito, Alfatih Sikki Manggabarani, Desmintari. (2020). Analysis of Leadership Behavior and Career Development (Study of Class I Special Non-TPI Immigration Office, West Jakarta). Ilomata International Journal of Management Vol. 1 No. 4. October 2020. P-ISSN: 2714-8971; E-ISSN: 2714-8963. <https://doi.org/10.52728/ijm.v1i4.165>.
- 5) Armstrong, Michael dan Angela Baron. (2011). Performance Management: The New Realities Developing Practice. London: Institute of Personal and Development.
- 6) Aulia Rahman, Muhammad Saleh Mire, Irsan Tri Cahyadinata. (2021). The Influence of Career Development and Servant Leadership towards Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance on PDAM Tirta Kencana Samarinda. Budapest International Research and Critics Institute-Journal Vol. 4 No. 3. 2021. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.33258/birci.v4i3.2437>.
- 7) Avolio, B. J., & Bass, B. M. (1994). Evaluate the impact of transformational leadership training at individual, group, organizational, and community levels (Final report to the W. K. Kellogg Foundation). Binghamton, NY: Binghamton University.
- 8) Bass, B. M & Riggio, R.E. (2006). Transformational Leadership - 2nd edition e-book. New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum.
- 9) Bernadin, H. John and Joyce E.A Russel. (2018). Human Resources Management. (An Experiential Approach International Edition). McGraw-Hill Inc.
- 10) Bülent Ulutürk dan Recep Tayfun. (2019). The Roles of Transformational Leadership, Communication Competence and Communication Satisfaction on Employees' Job Satisfaction. İletişim Kuram ve Araştırma Dergisi (Journal of Communication Theory and Research). Volume 2019, Issue 49, 48 - 68, 20.12.2019. Başkent University, Faculty of Communication, 0000-0001-7825-4711 Turkey.

- 11) Cecep Pahrudin, Sandriana Marina, Lira Agusinta. (2018). Ethical Leadership, Job Characteristics, and Job Satisfaction of Airline Employees. *Journal of Transportation & Logistics Management-Vol. 05 No. 02*, Juli 2018. <http://ejournal.stmt-trisakti.ac.id/index.php/jmtranslog>.
- 12) Cindy Christine Miranda, Sirajuddin, dan Akbar Gunawan. (2020). The Influence of Competence, Job Stress and Job Conflict on Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance in the Power Generation Industry. *Trisakti Industrial Engineering Journal*. Vol. 10 No. 1, March 2020. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.25105/jti.v10i1.8392>.
- 13) Colquitt, Jason A., Jeffrey A. LePine, dan Michael J. Wesson. (2015). *Organization Behavior*. New York: McGraw Hill.
- 14) Daryanto dan Bambang Suryanto. (2022). *Employee Performance Appraisal Management*. Special Edition. Yogyakarta: Gava Media.
- 15) Dessler, Gary. (2020). *Human Resource Management*. Sixteenth Edition. Florida.
- 16) Di Eh, Huang Chien-Jung, Chen I-Heng and Yu Te-Cheng. (2010). "Organizational Justice And Customer Citizenship Behavior Of Retail Industries". *The Service Industries Journal*. Vol 30 No. 11 (September). Pp 1919-1934.
- 17) Dyne, V.L, and Graham J.W. (2005). *Organizational Citizenship Behavior; Construct Redefinition Measurement and Validation*. *Academy Management Journal* 37, (4), 765-802).
- 18) Folger, R., Rosenfield, D., Grove, J., & Corkran, L. (1979). Effects Of "Voice" And Peer Opinions on Responses to Inequity. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 37, 2253–2261.
- 19) Gibson, J.L., J.M. Ivancevich, J. R. Donnelly Jr., Robert Konopaske. (2012). *Organizations: Behavior, Structure, Prcesses*, 14th Edition. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- 20) Greenberg, Jerald dan Robert A. Baron. (2010). *Behavior in Organization*. Tenth Edition. New York: Pearson.
- 21) Hair, Jr et.al. (2010). *Multivariate Data Analysis (7th ed)*. United States : Pearson.
- 22) Hartini. (2021). *Person Organization Fit (P-O Fit), Quality of Work Life dan Keadilan Organisasi*. Pekalongan, PT. Nasya Expanding Management.
- 23) Haryadi dan Nunung Nurhasanah. (2021). The Influence of Competence, Work Environment, Career Development on Job Satisfaction and Its Implications on Employee Performance at PT. Sukses Abadi Karya Inti Sragen Central Java. *Manajerial*, Vol. 20 No.2 Desember 2021, Hal - 319. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.17509/manajerial.v20i2.30188>.
- 24) Hassan Barau Singhry. (2018). Perceptions Of Leader Transformational Justice And Job Satisfaction In Public Organizations. *Emerald Insight. International Journal of Public Leadership*, Vol. 14 No. 2, pp. 80-95. 25 April 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPL-01-2018-0007>.
- 25) I Komang Triyana Dharma, I Wayan Sujana, dan Ni Nyoman Ari Novarini. (2021). The Influence of Career Development on Employee Performance with Transformational Leadership as a Moderating Variable at PT. Gapura Angkasa Denpasar. *Jurnal EMAS*. Vol. 2 No. 2. Februari 2021. E-ISSN : 2774-3020.
- 26) Jeong Rok Oh. (2013) *The Impact of Organizational Justice on Career Satisfaction*
- 27) Joreskog, Karl dan Sorbom Dag. (1996). *Lisrel 8: Users Reference Guide*, SSI, Inc.Chicago
- 28) Josiane Fahed-Sreih. (2020). *Career Development and Job Satisfaction*. Ebook (PDF) ISBN 978-183880-748-1. London: IntechOpen.
- 29) Khan, Junaid Athar, Shahid Jan, and Qadir Bakhsh Baloch. (2017). The Impact of Organizational Justice on Career Satisfaction of Employees in the Public Sector Organizations of Pakistan. *Journal of Managerial Sciences* 11.

- 30) Kreitner, Robert dan Angelo Kinicki. (2013). *Organizational Behavior*. 10th Edition. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- 31) Lambert, E., dan Hogan, N. (2008). The Importance of Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment in Shaping Turnover Intent A Test of a Causal Model. *Criminal Justice Review*.
- 32) Lira Agusinta, Aji Endra, Nugroho, Peppy Fachrial, Ryan Firdiansyah Suryawan. (2021). Employee Competency Study Model, Ground Support Equipment Effectiveness and Job Satisfaction Towards Service Quality of PT. Jasa Angkasa Semesta. *JTLA*, Issue 1, Nomor 1 (2021), 41-54. E-ISSN: 2807-145X P-ISSN: 2807-1522. Published by ABNUS Publisher. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.52909/jtla.v1i1.37>.
- 33) Minseo Kim, and Terry A. Beehr. (2016). Directing Our Own Careers, But Getting Help From Empowering Leaders. *Emerald Insight, International Journal of Career Development International*, Vol. 22 No. 3, pp. 300-317. 12 June 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CDI-11-2016-0202>.
- 34) Miston Mapuranga, Eugene Tafadzwa Maziriri, Tarisai Fritz Rukuni, and Thobekani Lose. (2021). Employee Organisational Commitment and the Mediating Role of Work Locus of Control and Employee Job Satisfaction: The Perspective of SME Workers. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management* 14:306. 5 July 2021. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm14070306>.
- 35) Mujanah, Siti. (2020). The Effect of Self-Efficacy, Competence, and Emotional Quotient on Employee Performance Through Career Development as an Intervening Variable on Companies. *Proceedings of the 17th International Symposium on Management (INSYMA, 2020)*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2991/aebmr.k.200127.012>.
- 36) Nadeem-Uz-Zaman, Ahmed, Tariqa, Ramayah, Thurasamy, Khalid, Zeeshana, and Asad, Muhammad. (2022). Career stages at the bottom line: Revisiting the relationship between organizational justice and turnover intentions. (Employees of public and private sectors in Pakistan). *Journal: Human Systems Management*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 155-172, 2022. DOI: 10.3233/HSM-211205.
- 37) Nenin Kartika Sari. (2019). The Influence of Perception of Organizational Support and Organizational Justice on Job Satisfaction. *Psikoborneo*, Vol 7, No 1, 2019: 120-128. ISSN: 2477-2666. E-ISSN: 2477-2674
- 38) Nita Tri Febrianti, Suharto, dan Wachyudi. (2020). The Effect of Career Development And Motivation on Employee Performance Through Job Satisfaction In PT. Jabar Jaya Perkasa. *International Journal of Business and Social Science Research*. Vol: 1, Issue: 2, October 2020. DOI: 10.47742/ijbssr.v1n2p3.
- 39) Nurul Aini, Toni Herlambang, Arik Susbiyani. (2020). The Impact of Employee Competence and Job Promotion on Employee Career Development and Performance. *Jurnal Sains Manajemen dan Bisnis Indonesia* Vol. 10 No. 2. 2020. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.32528/jsmbi.v10i2.4109>.
- 40) Okan, E., and Bayraktar, C.A. (2021). Analysis of the Relationship Between Organizational Justice and Job Satisfaction in the Airline Industry. In: Calisir, F. (eds) *Industrial Engineering in the Internet-of-Things World. GJCIE 2020. Lecture Notes in Management and Industrial Engineering*. Springer, Cham. 08 August 2021. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-76724-2_27.
- 41) Pribadi Widyatmojo, Purbudi Wahyuni dan Agus Haryadi. (2021). *Manajemen Sumberdaya Manusia Indonesia*. Teori dan aplikasi Penelitian. Edisi ke-1. Yogyakarta: Global Pustaka Utama dan FEB UPN Veteran Yogyakarta..
- 42) Rahman, A Fathorrahman dan Karnawati, T. A. (2020). The Influence of Job Satisfaction, Human Resource Practices and Labor Markets on Employees' Turnover Intentions. *Journal of Business and Management Concepts*, 6(2), pp. 164-178.
- 43) Rawan Alafeshat dan Cem Tanova. (2019). Servant Leadership Style and High-Performance Work System Practices: Pathway to a Sustainable Jordanian Airline Industry. *Journals MPDI - Sustainability* Volume 11, Issue 22, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11226191>.

- 44) Rees, Erik. (2001). Seven Principles of Transformational Leadership: Creating A Synergy of Energy. Diakses pada 13 November 2022. http://cicministry.org/commentary/issue85_warren_article.pdf.
- 45) Robbins, Stephen P., Judge, Timothy A. (2017). Organizational behavior 17th ed / Stephen P. Robbins, Timothy A. Judge (17th ed). Harlow: Pearson Education.
- 46) Rothwell, J.W., Stavros, M.J., Sullivan, L.R. (2016). Practicing Organization Development (Leading Transformation And Change). New Jersey: Hoboken.
- 47) Saraih U. N, Mohd Zaki M., , Mohd Karim K., Sakdan M. F., Amlus M. H. (2019). The Influences of Job Performance, Work-Life Balance And Organizational Justice on Employees' Career Satisfaction. (from one of the manufacturing companies in the North of Malaysia). Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews. eISSN: 2395-6518, Vol 7, No 5, 2019, pp 442-447. <https://doi.org/10.18510/hssr.2019.7549>.
- 48) Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2016). Research Methods For Business. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- 49) Sherwin Ian D. Pabustan, Mark Anthony M. Muldong, Dexter T. Yusi, Edhel P. Talplacido, Joanna May B. Zuñiga, and Joefil C. Jocson. (2021). Behavior Affecting the Performance of the Maintenance, Repair and Overhaul (MRO) Organization: A Case Study. International Journal of Progressive Research In Science And Engineering, Vol.2, No.11, November 2021. ISSN (Online): 2582-7898; SJIF: 5.494.
- 50) Simanungkalit, Yesa Martha Vita; Setyaningsih, Endang. (2019). The Influence of Leadership Style on Employee Job Satisfaction at PT. Lion Mentari Airlines. Jurnal Ekonomi Sakti (JES), [S.l.], v. 7, n. 2, p. 82-97, apr. 2019. ISSN 2685-1849. <https://jes.stie-sak.ac.id/index.php/103044/article/view/167>.
- 51) Siswono Haryono. (2017). SEM Methods for Management Research with AMOS, LISREL and PLS. East Jakarta: Luxima Metro Media.
- 52) Sobia Shabeer, Nadia Nasir, and Sumaria Rehman. (2020). *Inclusive Leadership And Career Adaptability: The Mediating Role Of Organization-Based Self-Esteem and The Moderating Role of Organizational Justice*. International Journal of Leadership in Education, 29 July 2020. DOI :10.1080/13603124.2020.1787524.
- 53) Spencer, M. Lyle & Spencer, M. Signe. (2008). Competence at Work: Models for Superior Performance. Canada: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- 54) Sugiyono. (2014). Administrative Research Methods. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- 55) Sugiyono. (2017). Administrative Research Methods - Complete with R&D Methods. Cetakan Ke-24, Bandung: Alfabeta.
- 56) Sugiyono. (2017). Business Research Methods - Quantitative, Qualitative, Combination, and R&D Approaches. 3rd Edition 1st Printing, Bandung: Alfabeta.
- 57) Sugiyono. (2019). Statistics For Research. Cetakan Ke-30, Bandung: Alfabeta.
- 58) Wahid Sumarjo. (2022). The Influence of Career Development and Placement on Job Satisfaction which Impacts Employee Performance at PT Sanco Perdika Pratama in Jakarta. JENIUS. Vol. 5, No. 2, Januari 2022. DOI:10.32493/JJSDM.v5i2.16524.
- 59) Warit Wipulanusat, Kriengsak Panuwatwanich and Rodney Anthony Stewart. (2018). Pathways to workplace innovation and career satisfaction in the public service: The role of leadership and culture. Emerald Insight, International Journal of Organizational Analysis, Vol. 26 No. 5, pp. 890-914. 5 November 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOA-03-2018-1376>.
- 60) Yusuf Ronny Edward dan Lila Maria Kaban. (2020). The Effect of Transformational Leadership and Competence on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as Intervening Variable. Academic Journal of Economic Studies. Vol. 6, No. 2, June 2020, pp. 62-72. ISSN 2393-4913, ISSN On-line 2457-5836. http://www.ajes.ro/wp-content/uploads/AJESarticle_1_330.pdf.